

Air quality control by under floor air distribution system

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AIM:

The main aim of this paper is to study the characteristics of indoor thermal environment under specified conditions and to improve its efficiency and study the System with separate return and exhaust air vents which effects the energy consumption and to get proper angle of the swirl inlet diffuser by comparison and the building heights to optimize of thermal stratification at design and operation stages and reduce the building energy consumption. To study the possibility of the under floor air distribution system usage in a dense occupied space (80 occupants) regarding to the general thermal comfort conditions and study the Different locations for the diffusers and velocities of the supply air are varied to determine what produces a better performance for the under floor air distribution system and the characteristics of thermal stratification in the UFAD system and the simplified model for calculating the airflows in the UFAD system and was to evaluate the performance of different ventilation systems in an aircraft cabin mockup.

KEYWORDS:

- Under floor air distribution system (UFAD).
- Return air vent height.
- Energy consumption reduction.
- Thermal comfort.
- Indoor air quality.
- Large indoor environment.
- Thermal Stratification.
- Air distribution performance index.
- Dense Occupied space.

INTRODUCTION:

Underfloor air distribution (UFAD) is an air distribution strategy for providing ventilation and space conditioning in buildings as part of the design of a HVAC system. UFAD systems use an underfloor supply plenum located between the structural concrete slab and a raised floor system to supply conditioned air through floor diffusers directly into the occupied zone of the building. Thermal stratification is one of the featured characteristics of UFAD systems, which allows higher thermostat setpoints compared to the traditional overhead systems (OH). UFAD cooling load profile is different from a traditional OH system due to the impact of raised floor, particularly UFAD may have a higher peak cooling load than that of OH systems. This is because heat is gained from building penetrations and gaps within the structure itself.

- UFAD has several potential advantages over traditional overhead systems, including layout flexibility, improved thermal comfort, improved ventilation efficiency, improved energy efficiency in suitable climates and reduced life cycle costs. UFAD is often used in office buildings, particularly highly-reconfigurable and open plan offices where raised floors are desirable for cable management. UFAD is appropriate for a number of different building types including commercials, schools, churches, airports, museums, libraries etc. Careful considerations need to be made in the construction phase of UFAD systems to ensure a well-sealed plenum to avoid air leakage in UFAD supply plenums.
- Bauman and Webster [1] showed that UFAD has several benefits, such as reduced building life cycle cost, improved thermal comfort, improved ventilation efficiency and indoor air quality (IAQ), reduced energy use, reduced floor to floor height in new construction and improved productivity and health of the occupant in the indoor space.
- Wang et al. [2] investigated the thermal stratification characteristics in a real-scale space with UFAD system. Their experimental results show that there are 4 zones in the vertical thermal stratification space. Namely, they are bottom cooler zone, lower narrow zone, transitional zone, and upper warmer zone.
- Alajmi and El-Amer [3] investigated the energy consumption of UFAD systems in commercial buildings for various types of application and at different air supply temperatures in a hot climate. Their results show that UFAD systems have a significant energy saving compared to ceiling-based air distribution (CBAD) systems, especially for high ceiling buildings.
- Webster et al. [4] showed the impact of supply air flow rate and supply air temperature of UFAD system on the thermal stratification in the indoor environment. As the supply air flow rate increases, room air stratification decreases. When the supply air temperature changes, the vertical temperature profile does not change, but shifts to the higher or lower temperature direction.

METHODS USED TO IMPROVE EFFICIENCY:

- Model description
- Simulation method
- Thermal comfort index based method
- Local thermal discomfort
- IAQ
- Energy consumption reduction in an UFAD system
- Typical commercial building configurations
- Thermal comfort assessment methods
- Numerical procedure validation
- Ratio of diffuser momentum to thermal plume buoyancy
- Experimental approach

METHODS AND REASONS:

1. Model description:

- In the year 2015, Kobayashi and Chen selected a room of dimensions of 5.16m length, 3.65m width and 2.27m height as shown in the fig.1.1 and conducted experiment at temperature 19 Celsius and flow rate is 4.4 ACH. The conditioned cool air is

delivered into the room by swirl diffusers located at the floor elevation assuming average static pressure is same as atmospheric pressure. As the proper specifications of boundary conditions and selection of turbulence model are the most vital factors on affecting the air flow. So, Model description is conducted in the selected dimensions.

FIG.1.2.Configuration of the model room.

2. **Simulation Method:**

Airpak 2.0 is adopted as the main simulating tool, which is an accurate, quick and easy to use design tool that simplifies design. Simulation method on the principle that the finite volume method with structured grid is adopted in solving procedure, and semi implicit method for pressure-linked equations algorithm is applied in resolving the pressure and velocity coupling. As its program cost will be less to assume at different conditions and good accuracy. So simulation method is conducted to obtain better results with low cost.

3. **Thermal comfort index based method:**

The condition of mind which expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment. Therefore, Fanger’s model combines the following four physical variables: air temperature, air velocity, mean radiant temperature, and the relative humidity and the two personal variables of clothing insulation and activity level into PMV1 index in order to predict the thermal comfort conditions. These PMV indices used to survey thermal comfort conditions of occupants by dividing room into regions i.e. occupied zone in standing mode (0-1.7m) and occupied zone in sitting mode (0-1.3m). All heat sources have a naturally occurring thermal plume which vacuums cooler air from the floor and distributes it upwards due to the upward motion of the warmer air generated by the heat sources. so the thermal comfort index should be considered.

Table 3.1:
Case study at three different swirl inlet angle:

Case study	30deg.		45deg.		60deg.							
	0-1.3m	0-1.7m	0-1.3m	0-1.7m	0-1.3m	0-1.7m						
	PPD	PMV	PPD	PMV	PPD	PMV						
1	16.9	-0.7	14.5	-0.6	26	-1	23.1	-0.9	26.3	-1.1	25.5	-0.93
2	14.1	-0.5	12.2	-0.4	23.4	-0.9	20.1	-0.8	24.4	-0.95	23.2	-0.86
3	10.4	-0.2	9.9	-0.1	16.5	-0.6	14.5	-0.4	21	-0.8	19.3	-0.7
4	10.6	-0.1	11.1	+0.1	15.3	-0.5	13.7	-0.3	20.1	-0.7	18.4	-0.7

The table 3.1 shows the data of the indices when the experiment is conducted with different swirl angles at 30deg. , 45deg. , 60deg. respectively.

5 Local thermal discomfort evaluation:

Air temperature normally increases with the height above the floor. If this increase is sufficiently high, the local warm discomfort can be felt at the head and/or the cold discomfort can be felt at the feet, although the body as a whole is thermally neutral. This localized and unwanted hot/cold feeling is called local thermal discomfort. Ghassem Heidarinejad., Mohammad Hassan Fathollahzadeh., and Hadi Pasdarsahri at 2015 were taken four case studies as shown in table 4.1 with two occupants and concluded that Max. Allowable vertical temp. Difference is 3 celsius between head and ankles. As the human comfort is very important for life. On considering local thermal discomfort, humans will not feel the hot/cold temperature

Table 4.1:
Temp. Gradient (Celsius) between the head and ankles heights of occupants:

Case study	occupant 1	occupant 2
1	1.1	1.7
2	1.4	2.1
3	2.5	3.4
4	2.8	3.6

Table 4.1 gives the data about the temperature differences as it is increasing as the increase in return air vent position.

6 Indoor Air Quality evaluation:

It is the average lifetime of the air at a particular location in the room relative to the time when it first entered the room. This indicates the air freshness. It is also called as mean local age of air. Ghassem Heidarinejad., Mohammad Hassan Fathollahzadeh., and Hadi Pasdarsahri at 2015 were taken four case studies as shown in table 5.1 and measured this index at the height of 1.1m from floor which is the breathing zone of the occupants

Table 5.1:
Mean local age of air in seconds at the height 1.1m from floor for occupants:

Case study	occupant 1	occupant 2
1	200	187
2	177	205
3	287	310
4	398	359

Table 5.1 explains mean local age of air in seconds at the height 1.1m from floor for occupants and observed that in case 1 and case 2, index is getting best results and in case 3 and case 4, some of the fresh air directly returned to the ventilation system without reaching the breathing zone.

7 Energy consumption Reduction:

- In the year 2015, Cheng found that the cooling coil load in an UFAD system is reduced in relation to that of MV system
- $Q_{coil} - UFAD = Q_{coil} - MV - C_p \times Me \times (T_e - T_{set})$ --- 1
- $Q_{coil} - MV = Q_{space} + Q_{vent}$ --- 2

Where $Q_{coil} - MV$ and $Q_{coil} - UFAD$ are the cooling coil load for MV system and UFAD system, respectively

Q_{space} and Q_{vent} are the space cooling load and the ventilation load,

T_e (°C) is the exhaust air temperature

T_{set} (°C) is the set-point air temperature for the room in the occupied zone,

C_p (J/kgK) is the heat capacity of air and Me (kg/s) is the exhaust air flow rate.

Based on Eqs. (1) and (2), it is obvious that $C_p \times Me \times (T_e - T_{set})$ is the reduced cooling coil load in an UFAD system

- As Energy consumption reduction increases by reducing the height of return air vent from ceiling to floor height, They conducted case studies to get the specified height to maximum energy consumption reduction.

8 Typical commercial building configurations:

Three different building applications of common commercial buildings were virtually designed. First, a typical office building has been chosen as an example, single floor building with total floor area of (30*15 = 450 m²) with 2.4 m height. The longer side of building is initially oriented towards a north direction. The second building type was proposed for a community center or wor-ship building, with same floor area and height of 4.8 m (double the office building height). While, the third building

was designed for height of 7.2 m (triple the office building height) with same floor area; this could be a hotel lobby, airport, or showroom building. A schematic diagram is shown in fig 7.1

- **Fig 7.1(a):**

- **Fig 7.1(b):**

- **Fig 7.1(c):**

The Fig 7.1 represents the buildings with different heights.

- **Graph 7.1:** A typical year's energy consumption (MJ) for the example building for height of 2.4m.

- **Graph 7.2:** A typical year's energy consumption (MJ) for the example building for height of 4.8 m.

- Graph 7.3: A typical year's energy consumption (MJ) for the example building for height of 7.2 m.
- Graph 7.1, 7.2, 7.3 shows energy consumption for different heights of buildings.

9 Thermal comfort assessment methods:

- Thermal comfort field survey- To assess the overall occupants' thermal comfort during the summer months of a building served by a UFAD system. It was distributed among 40 occupants, 20 male and 20 female, of varying ages, from 25 to 60 years and measured true feelings
- CFD model- The numerical model used for the tested room was constructed using the “Design Builder” software, which gives detailed 3-D air flow and temperature distributions in building.
- An assessment of these thermal comfort responses clearly shows that the occupants are facing some problems with the UFAD system in its current settings. More analysis needs to be done in order to capture the source(s) of discomfort accurately

10 Ratio of diffuser momentum to thermal plume buoyancy:

- Lin and Linden stated, the controlling parameters on the indoor air stratification were the momentum flux of the cooling jets (M) and the buoyancy flux of the heat source (B) Based on the DMTPB ratio the thermal stratification is been counted and so that the quality of the air will increased by increase in the ratio.

$$T = \frac{(M_3)^4}{(B_1 \times A_1)^2}$$

Where T is the ratio which indicates the performance of stratification

11 Experimental approach:

- The cabin mockup had seven rows with a single aisle. The seat pitch is 760 mm. Forty-two thermal manikins were placed in the seats and simulated the effect of the passenger positions on the airflow patterns and the height of the seat is 1.4m. The supply air temperature was controlled at 19.5 °C. The fresh air is supplied by static pressure box from the bottom inlets of the cabin. The static pressure box can make inlet velocity more uniform. Then, exhaust to outdoor through the cabin ceiling. Based upon the comfort of the passengers the temperature and the height will be modified

Fig 10.1: Experimental cabin mockup:

- Fig 10.1 shows the model of the air craft cabin.

RESULTS:

After studying all the methods, the following conclusions are arrived:

- Among all the swirl inlet angles i.e., 30°, 45° and 60°. At 30°, the vertical air movement is very less and the diffuser discharge is relatively horizontal in comparison with the time.
- The suggestible value of this thermal comfort index is between -0.5 and +0.5.
- The energy consumption reduction increases by reducing the height of return air vent from ceiling to floor height.
- The Maximum Allowable vertical temperature Difference is 3 Celsius between head and ankles.
- PMV-PPD indices are used to survey thermal comfort conditions of occupants.
- On installing the return air vent in the height at 1.3m from the floor in an UFAD system leads to a 15.3% reduction in energy consumption in comparison with the MV system.
- A swirl inlet diffuser with the return air vent position at 1.7 m from the floor height causes to the favorable results.
- The amount of saving is increased as the building height increases.
- UFAD system can save up to 30% energy compared to CBAD and It is recommended to use UFAD to save energy increase IAQ.
- Over 90% improvement of thermal comfort from the current was realized at a supply air temperature of 21 °C and velocity of 1 m/s.
- The CFD model provides useful analysis for different operating conditions without the need to change settings on the ground and re-take measurements
- Mean velocity of the occupied zone is less than 0.8m/s and the mean local age of air is increased by reducing the supply air velocity, which means that there is a less fresh air in the breathing zone
- If it is auxiliary side air supply in the air craft cabin, the performance can be improved

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